

INTEGRATION OF PRIMARY EDUCATION DISCIPLINES LEARNING PROBLEM

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Abstract: *The article analyze the problems of integrative teaching of primary education subjects.*

Key words: *education, primary, training science, integration, problem, knowledge, skills, approaches.*

The teaching process in the education system of Uzbekistan is being improved on the basis of national experience the curlyadopted legal and regulatory documents on education relevant in this. For example, “National Qualifications Framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan” approved by the Resolution of the cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, № 287 of May 15. 2020 [1] provides for the formation of following eight qualification levels for students:

1. Impart knowledge in the field of labor or education.
2. Impart special knowledge in the field of labor or education.
3. Impart general knowledge of the principles, processes and general concepts in the field of labor or education.
4. Impart a wide range of practical and theoretical knowledge covering the general field of work or study.
5. Provide comprehensive specialized and theoretical knowledge in the field of labor or education understanding the limits of such as knowledge.
6. Impart advanced knowledge in the field of labor education, including critical understanding of theory and the most important principles.
7. Impart highly specialized knowledge some of which is important in the field of labor or education and s the pans for original and critical thinking in mind fields.
8. Impart highly specialized knowledge in the advances field of work or study and I interdisciplinary.

It should be noted that in addition to the state educational standards and qualification requirements, the teaching of primary education subjects should be based on the skills set out in this National Qualifications Framework. Because according to the requirements set in the national Qualifications Framework primary school student are required to be provided with general, special, theoretical, practice, advanced and focused knowledge. It should be noted that concept of general knowledge is to provide complete information on the subject, the special concept into provide in depth information on the subject the theoretical concept is to form students' scientific thinking in the subject, the practical concept is to form students' ability to apply what they learned in the subject. Concept of extension and orientation means increasing the interest of student n academic subjects. Therefore, the National skills framework is one of the integrated teaching of academic disciplines. One of the innovative approaches to imparting such knowledge to primary school students at an early stages through the teaching sciences in the integrated teaching factor. There we understand your attention to the analysis of the need for integrated teaching of primary education.

At present accordance with the state educational standard of general secondary education, approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2017 No. 187, at the stage of primary education of the primary education of the country are taught:

/p	Educational sciences	Classes								Weekly total hours	
	State owned classes										
	Reading and mother tongue			0	0						36
	Calligraphy										4
	Uzbek /russian language										6
	Foreign language										6
	Mathematics										20
	Education										4
	Music culture										4
	Fine arts										4
	Technology										4
	The world around us and natural sciences										4
	Physical education										8
	School hours	5									0.5

1-table:

It should be noted that in the primary education system of the country are thought the basics of the subjects taught in the later stages of education these disciplines selected and put into practice on the basis of the following principles:

Firstly, national pedagogical experiences were taken into account in the choice of subjects;

Secondly, primary education curricula meet the requirements of international education programs such as TIMSS and STEAM;

Thirdly, these subjects correspond to the age, physical, mental, and aesthetic capabilities of primary school students;

Fourthly, the subjects are aimed at preparing students for the subjects taught in the later stages of education ;

Fifthly, hours are also lifted in the school account to decline the mastery of academic subjects.

So, it is important to achieve the quality and effectiveness of education through the integrated teaching of these disciplines.

1. The need for integrated teaching of primary education is determined by:

1. Exact sciences.....
2. Natural sciences...
3. Humanities ...

Our country has a unique experience in teaching this category of subject in primary education. At the same time, it would be expedient to rely on interdisciplinary integrated teaching to further improve their teaching and increase teaching efficiency. If you notice you will understand that to develop students independent thinking work and physical skills the world around and the natural sciences provide students with knowledge about the universe, nature, flora and fauna at an early stage and build their ecological skills.

So there is a need to organize. The teaching process in primary education in an interdisciplinary way.

2. The need for interdisciplinary relevance of academic disciplines . There is a need to ensure interdisciplinary relevance of academic disciplines in the specific natural and humanities category as well. There are also certain experience in this regard. For example in the subject of reading and mother tongue, when preparing students to the interdisciplinary relevance of academic discipline. To do this, the following results are expected:

1. Cooperation of developers of education subjects.

2. Avoid duplication in the choice of topics in a particular subject and take in to account the continuation of topics in the later stages of education.

3. Scientific and pedagogical examination of selected topics.

Such as approach allows for the students to write a statement or essay the method of composing sentences based on reading texts and determining the correctness of the structured sentences based on the grammar of the native languages is used. By developing such as experienced methodologies it is possible to from an Interdisciplinary connection between the object of primary education.

This approach provide unique educational opportunities. Especial approach is required to ensure effective organization of the interdisciplinary interdependence of the subjects of primary education. Therefore the education center of the ministry of republic education of republic of Uzbekistan should take the intuitive and implement in this regard.

3. The need for interdependence of teaching materials in textbooks this issue is also relevant which requires supplementing the content of educational materials in textbooks in reaching knowledge and information through each educational material. The integration of textbook materials based on an important role in updating the information and knowledge in them especially in the creation of electronic modular versions of textbooks.

1. Examination of textbooks by specialists and practically experienced teaches

2. Review of materials of related educational disciplines and avoid duplication

2. Regular improvement of textbooks.

In our opinion, adherence to them leads to the independence of facing materials.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

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